

Analysis of Perceptions of Socioeconomic Determinants of Gender-Based Violence in Africa: A Multilevel Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a multi-level analysis of the determinants of gender-based violence in Africa using a subjective approach. The study aims to examine the factors that influence gender violence and to understand their role in African society. The results highlight individual determinants such as poverty and the experience of harassment, as well as social and political determinants such as the presence of government and the police. Economic analysis of the results reveals the importance of combating poverty and promoting women's economic empowerment in reducing gender violence in Africa. The economic implications also highlight the role of the media and social networks in raising awareness of this problem. In conclusion, this article contributes to the understanding of the determinants of gender violence in Africa and calls for strategic interventions to prevent and reduce this worrying phenomenon.

KEYWORDS: Gender violence, Africa, Subjective approach, Multilevel analysis, Poverty.

JEL codes: D 13, I 32, J 16, O 55

1. INTRODUCTION

In both traditional and modern society, women's marginal position is a factor in violence, harassment and discrimination. (Ndiaye, 2021). The consequences of conjugal violence are divorce and the well-being of children. Gender-based violence (GBV) is indeed a worrying phenomenon worldwide, with significant repercussions on the health and well-being of women and girls. This is all the more true when we consider the United Nations (UN) definition, according to which GBV is "any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or mental harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life" (Sandis, 2006).

In developing countries, and particularly in Africa, forms of violence are even more prevalent due to social inequalities, crises and ever-increasing poverty. Existing statistics on the subject show that women are more at risk than men when it comes to forms of Gender-Based Violence (GBV). Moreover, one in three women (03) has been raped, beaten, coerced into sex or abused at least once in her life (Martin, 2006).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and the World Bank, domestic violence is the leading cause of death and ill-health among women aged between 16 and 44, more so than cancer, malaria or road accidents (Krug, Dahlberg, Mercy, & et al., 2002).

In Africa, rates of GBV are particularly high, with devastating consequences for communities and economies. Yet, in recent years, the fight against GBV has gradually made its way onto the political agendas of African states. Green numbers, women's ministries and financial empowerment programs are just some of the measures African countries have taken to demonstrate their commitment to women's rights to international donors. However, these gender policies are struggling to produce effective results. Despite significant progress in raising awareness of the problem and implementing policies to protect women, GBV persists in many African countries (Ndiaye, 2021). In 2018, a WHO survey revealed that 65% of women in Central Africa and 40% in West Africa have experienced violence. These figures account for reported violence.

Indeed, fear of stigmatization often discourages victims from reporting their abuser. Society's perception of GBV can create

a large gap between the number of reported victims and the total number of victims. Previous studies have identified several socio-economic factors that contribute to GBV in Africa (Ryckmans & Maquestiau 1, 2008; Abramsky, Watts, & Garcia-Moreno, 2011) But few studies have examined society's own perceptions of violence against women and its determinants. What's more, despite the scale of the problem, most available studies are limited to developed countries (Garcia-Moreno, et al., 2013; Bleck, Palermo, & Peterman , 2014; Abrahams, Jewkes, Laubscher , & Hoffman, 2006). The few studies carried out in Africa have focused on a regionally restricted population (Garcia-Moreno, Jansen, Ellsberg, Heise, & Watts, 2006).. To this end, certain limitations, notably the overestimation of prevalence, have been raised in the literature. Hence the purpose of this study. Based on a more representative population, this study attempts to analyze the determinants of gender-based violence. By focusing on the population's perception, in contrast to previous studies, it will specifically analyze (i) the effect of socio-economic characteristics on GBV, (ii) the effect of cultural weight on GBV and (iii) the effect of national policy on GBV. The analysis of these determinants of GBV in Africa is a complex and multidimensional research topic, requiring a rigorous methodological approach to apprehend the complexity of socio-economic, cultural and political factors that contribute to GBV. To this end, we use a multi-level model to analyze the interactions between regional and national factors that influence GBV in Africa.

Using the multilevel model, we expect differences in levels to be explained by socio-cultural and economic characteristics within each country (intra-group variance effect). On the other hand, the legal and political norms implemented as part of policies to protect women and girls against violence have an influence on their well-being and development. This approach should lead to the identification of other complementary parameters not hitherto taken into account for effective policies to combat gender-based violence in Africa. We also assume that these factors are interconnected and mutually influential.

By examining people's perceptions of these factors, we hope to gain a better understanding of how these factors interact to influence gender-based violence in Africa.

In order to achieve this, this article will be structured as follows. Section 2 is a summary review of the literature and highlights the interest of our approach, which consists in using a multi-level approach based on regional characteristics. In the third section, we present our methodology. The fourth section presents data on people's perceptions of GBV in African countries and the variables used in this work. Section 5 is a presentation and analysis of the results obtained, before concluding in section 6.

2. BRIEF REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE ON GBV

Gender-based violence is a major challenge to the health and well-being of the population (Vyas & Watts, 2009). It includes a variety of behaviors ranging from physical and sexual abuse to verbal and psychological violence. Several consequences on physical and mental health, interpersonal relationships, employment and economic development (WHO, 2013) affect victims.

Although the problem is global in nature (Garcia-Moreno, et al., 2013) many studies link the problem to socio-economic vulnerability and low levels of education in developing countries, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (Abramsky, Watts, & Garcia-Moreno, 2011).

Several studies have attempted to understand the determinants of this violence.

Work in this area can be grouped into two categories. Those that focus on individual factors and those that emphasize the role of social factors as the main determinants of GBV.

2.1. Individual factors

Individual factors play an important role as determinants of GBV in Africa. Several studies have examined these factors and identified their influence on the prevalence and perpetuation of GBV. Among these individual factors, there are some that favor GBV:

- Previous victimization experiences: women who have been victims of violence in the past have a high probability of being victims of GBV again. (Jewkes R. , 2002).

- Individual attitudes and beliefs: These also play a role in perpetuating GBV. Men and women who hold sexist attitudes, justify violence or adhere to rigid gender stereotypes are more likely to perpetrate or tolerate violent behavior (Fufu, Jewkers, & Roselli Tim et al., 2013).

- Mental health: Individuals' mental health can also be an influential factor in GBV. Studies have shown that men and women suffering from mental health problems, such as depression or post-traumatic stress disorder, are more likely to be involved in acts of GBV (Caron & Guay, 2005).

- Psychological factors: sexist attitudes, rigid gender roles and beliefs that justify violence play a key role in perpetuating GBV. Studies have shown that negative attitudes and beliefs towards women and the justification of violence are associated with an increased risk of gender-based violence (Jewkes R. , Sikweyiya, Morrell, & Dunkle, 2011; Mekonnen & Abeya, 2019).

These different factors can contribute to a continuous spiral of violence. On the other hand, other individual factors are considered to be real obstacles to GBV. These include

- Education: The level of education can play a protective role against GBV in Africa. Women with a higher level of education are often better informed of their rights, more financially independent and have more resources to escape situations of violence (Johnson & Kishor, 2004).

- Economic independence: Women's economic empowerment has been identified as a protective factor against GBV. Women who have paid employment or an independent source of income are less likely to be victims of violence, as they have more means to escape abusive relationships (Antai & Adaji, 2012; Peterman, Palermo, & Bredekamp, 2011).

2.2. Social factors :

Social factors, rooted in social norms, values and structures, can contribute to the perpetuation of GBV. Research has identified certain social factors as key influences on GBV:

- Gender norms and social roles: Social norms and expectations towards women and men can fuel GBV in Africa. Gender stereotypes, such as the idea of male superiority and the weight of tradition, enforcing female submission, contribute to the perpetuation of power inequalities between the sexes, which in turn fosters violence ((Dwokin, Hatcher, & Colvin Chris et al., 2013; Jewkes, Sikweyiya, & Morell, 2011).

- Power inequalities: Power inequalities between men and women are a central factor in GBV in Africa. Unbalanced social structures and power relations, often grant men greater control over women's resources, decision-making and lives, which can lead to situations of violence ((Fufu, Jewkers, & Roselli Tim et al., 2013; Jewkes R. , 2002). Violence is often used as a means of maintaining and reinforcing this inequality of power.

- Cultural norms: Traditional cultural practices can also contribute to the perpetuation of GBV in Africa. Practices such as early marriage, female genital mutilation and dowry-related violence are often rooted in cultural norms that reinforce gender inequalities and justify violence ((Yount & Carrera, 2006). However, it is important to note that these practices are not intrinsically linked to African culture, but rather to specific traditions in certain regions.

- Peer and community influence: Social norms within communities can influence the prevalence of GBV in Africa. Studies have shown that violent behavior is sometimes perceived as acceptable or justified within certain social groups, which can normalize violence (Antai & Adaji, 2012). Peer pressure and community expectations can also influence the perpetration and tolerance of GBV.

- Socio-economic conditions: Socio-economic conditions, such as poverty and limited access to education and employment, can also contribute to the prevalence of GBV in Africa. Economic inequalities can reinforce power inequalities between the sexes, which can increase the risk of violence ((Amber, Palermo, & Bredekamp, 2011; Jewkes, Sikweyiya, & Morell, 2011).

- Gender norms and power inequalities: Prevailing gender norms and power inequalities between men and

women contribute to the perpetuation of gender violence in Africa. Socially constructed expectations of gender roles, male control and male dominance reinforce gender violence ((Dwokin, Hatcher, & Colvin Chris et al., 2013; Fufu, Jewkers, & Roselli Tim et al., 2013).

Understanding and addressing these factors is essential to preventing and reducing GBV in Africa. Interventions must aim to challenge restrictive gender norms, promote gender equality, strengthen women's rights and create more inclusive and respectful social environments.

However, to our knowledge, few studies have taken a subjective approach to analyzing the determinants of GBV. The subjective approach, based on data collected directly from populations, enables us to better understand their perception of the socio-economic determinants of gender-based violence. Qualitative research, has revealed that women identify economic inequality, financial pressures and patriarchal norms as important factors contributing to gender-based violence (Dequiré, 2019).

Also, despite its relevance in such situations, to the best of our knowledge, multilevel analysis, which examines individual, community and societal factors simultaneously and offers a more holistic perspective on gender-based violence in Africa, has only rarely been used for this type of study in Africa, including work on Ethiopia (Tiruye, Harris, Chojentya, & al., 2020)Uganda (Igulut, 2022) which have tackled GBV using this approach. They showed that GBV is influenced by individual factors (age, education), community factors (social norms) and societal factors (policies and laws). By integrating qualitative and quantitative data, our study aims to deepen understanding of the socio-economic determinants of existing regional disparities in GBV in Africa.

By integrating these data and academic works, our article proposes a robust and grounded approach to analyzing the socio-economic determinants of gender-based violence in Africa, highlighting women's perspectives and examining factors at different levels. This contributes to a better understanding of this complex phenomenon and can provide the basis for more targeted and effective interventions.

3. ECONOMETRIC APPROACH

As mentioned in the literature, in a given environment (here, the region¹), gender-based violence cannot be explained by a single factor. It stems from the interaction of several factors at different levels, such as individual characteristics, interpersonal relationships, social norms and institutional structures. This type of problem, which concerns the relationships between factors identified at different hierarchical levels, is a multi-level problem. (Hox, 1995).

An analysis of GBV at only one hierarchical level is

¹ Territory of a country whose variable extent is also determined by a cultural community.

insufficient to formulate hypotheses at the regional level. Indeed, individuals belong to a region, with cultures, habits and customs that sometimes differ from one region to another within the same country. These regions are then nested within a country, and tend to share certain common values and policies (Arzenšek, Košmrlj, & Širca, 2014). Thus, the violence experienced by women in a given region is not only the result of the individual characteristics of the region, but also of certain cultural and/or national variables. Depending on the hierarchical structure of the problem, using classical regression methods to analyze perceptions of the socio-economic determinants of gender-based violence in African regions could lead to biased results. The use of multilevel models allows us to deal with these statistical problems.

Alongside the classic regression model (Novak & Marko, 2017) the multi-level model has the advantage of taking into account the social, economic, cultural and political context in which gender-based violence occurs. It makes it possible to analyze how the individual characteristics and behaviors of regions are shaped by the cultural norms, structural inequalities and implemented gender policies to which they belong. This contextualization is essential for understanding the root causes of GBV in Africa, and developing effective interventions at regional and/or national level.

Despite the need for a multi-level modeling approach, this method is rarely used. A major advantage of using a two-level model rather than a standard single-level regression is that several effects can be differentiated in a single model: the main effects of context or macro-level variables, the main effects of individual-level variables, and any interaction effects between the two levels. Multilevel models also make it possible to deal with complex variations at different levels - they do not consider regions or countries to have the same error variance (Schyns, 2002).

In this study, depending on the structure of our data, the model will be broken down into two levels: the empty model, level 1 (region level) and level 2 (country level).

The "empty" model will be estimated in order to study the variance in the frequency of GBV between countries and within a country. To this end, the decomposition of the variance into random effects makes it possible to estimate the share of intra-group (country) variance in the total variance. It also expresses the degree of similarity between individuals within the same group (Country). The specification of the empty model is as follows:

$$Y_{ij} = \beta_{00} + \mu_{0j} + \varepsilon_{ij} \tag{1}$$

$$V(Y) = \sigma_{\varepsilon}^2 + \sigma_{\mu_0}^2 \tag{2}$$

The empty model (equation 1) consists of two parts: a fixed part β_{00} which represents the overall mean of Y; and a random part made up of the two error terms ε_{ij} and μ_{0j} .

$V(Y)$ represents the total variance of Y, composed of the within-class variance (σ_{ε}^2) and inter-class variance ($\sigma_{\mu_0}^2$).

The variance decomposition formula enables us to assess the share of variance to be attributed to each of the two (2)

levels. The share of variance attributed to each level is shown below.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\sigma_{\varepsilon}^2}{V(Y)} & \text{Niveau 1 (région)} \\ \frac{\sigma_{\mu_0}^2}{V(Y)} & \text{Niveau 2 (pays)} \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

The context of our study focuses on the manifestation of GBV at the level of administrative regions (level 1), which in turn is located in a Country (level 2). Since each of these levels is likely to have an effect on GBV, the model takes into account variables linked to each level. It is presented as follows:

Level 1:

$$Y_{ij} = \alpha_{0j} + \alpha_{1j}X_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \tag{4}$$

Where Y_{ij} represents the GBV level of the $i^{\text{ème}}$ region of the $j^{\text{ème}}$ country. An index j is associated with the coefficients α_0 and α_1 . This indicates that these coefficients may vary from one environment to another. ε_{ij} represents the random error for each region i of country j ; with $\varepsilon_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma_{\varepsilon}^2)$.

At level 2, the aim is to show that the coefficients α_{0j} and α_{1j} are random by introducing the random error terms μ_{0j} and μ_{1j} . (Bressoux, 2007)

Level 2:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_{0j} = \beta_{00} + \mu_{0j} \\ \alpha_{1j} = \beta_{10} + \mu_{1j} \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

Replacing equations (5) in equation (4) gives the following equation:

$$Y_{ij} = \beta_{00} + \beta_{10}X_{ij} + (\mu_{0j} + \mu_{1j}X_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij}) \tag{6}$$

With β_{00} which represents the overall mean of Y, β_{10} which is the average regression slope for all countries. μ_{0j} represents a random error associated with each country j , assumed to be normally distributed, with mean zero and variance $\sigma_{\mu_0}^2$. μ_{1j} represents the deviation of each country from the mean. It is a random variable with mean zero and variance $\sigma_{\mu_1}^2$. ε_{ij} represents the random error associated with each region i of country j .

The formulation of the full model, i.e. with simultaneous consideration of Level 1 and Level 2 explanatory variables, is presented below. This more complete model presents the main constants, slopes and interaction effects between the different levels.

$$\alpha_{0j} = \beta_{00} + \beta_{01}Z_j + \mu_{0j} \text{ and } \alpha_{1j} = \beta_{10} + \beta_{11}Z_j + \mu_{1j} \tag{7}$$

With Z_j , the variables associated with level 2 (Country). By replacing (7) in equation (4), we obtain the complete two-level multilevel model as follows:

$$Y_{ij} = \beta_{00} + \beta_{01}Z_j + \beta_{10}X_{ij} + \beta_{11}X_{ij}Z_j + (\mu_{0j} + \mu_{1j}X_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij}) \tag{8}$$

The model in equation (8) will be estimated as described above, taking into account contextual effects. This will avoid errors of over- or under-estimation of the impact of

the various variables.

4. DATA SOURCE AND VARIABLES USED

In this section, our analysis focuses on data sources, variables and descriptive statistics.

4.1. Data source

The data used in this study come from the 9th series of surveys carried out by the Afrobarometer network over the period 2022-2023. Afrobarometer is a pan-African, non-partisan survey research network that produces data on African people's experiences and assessments of democracy, governance and quality of life. Data from 20 countries, disaggregated into 305 administrative regions, will be used for further analysis. The use of these data will enable us to understand the regional and national factors influencing GBV in Africa.

4.2. Variables used

In order to analyze the socio-economic determinants of gender-based violence in Africa, certain variables were selected on the basis of the information available in the Afrobarometer databases and the literature on GBV. These variables are grouped into three categories: variables relating to the individual in the region, variables relating to the individual's community and variables relating to the government's gender policy.

In the group of variables relating to individuals, the following variables are retained:

The average age of the population surveyed in the region (**Age**). The proportion of people living in urban areas (**Urban**). The level of education (**Eduction**), which represents the proportion of people in the region who have completed secondary school. Poverty level (**Pauvreté**), measured by a composite indicator comprising 5 variables: lack of income, lack of fuel, lack of medical care, lack of drinking water and lack of food. This variable is calculated using the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) method. This method produces a poverty score ranging from 0 to 1, with 0 being identical to the absence of poverty in the region and 1 to extreme poverty in the region. The use of social networks (**Reseaux_sociaux**), represented by the proportion of the

population in the region who declare having used social networks at least once a month for information. Information via traditional media such as radio, television and the written press (**Media**), represented by the proportion of people who said they used the media at least a few times a month for information.

To measure the level of unemployment in the region, the variable **Unemployment** is used. This variable measures the proportion of unemployed people in the region. Consideration of GBV by the police (**Ps_police**), measured by the proportion of people who said that women who report GBV to the police are somewhat or taken seriously by the national police. Government presence in the region is measured by the variable **Presence_gov**, which represents the proportion of people who reported the existence of a government entity in the region (town halls, prefectures and other state bodies). The proportion of people in the region reporting the presence of at least one police or gendarmerie station in their locality is represented by the variable **Presence_police**. Government efforts in gender policy (**Effort_gov**) is measured by the proportion of people who recognize that their government is making efforts for women's rights and equality in the country. The variable **Harcel**, represents the proportion of people in the region who said that women who report gender-based violence are criticized or harassed by society. The level of democracy (**Democracy**) is measured as the proportion of people who consider their country to be democratic.

In this study, the explanatory variable is the perception of the extent of gender-based violence (**GBV**). This variable measures the proportion of people in the region declaring that women or girls are slightly less (or very frequently) victims of violence.

4.3. Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics show that two out of five people (39%) surveyed believe that gender-based violence is very common or slightly common in Africa (Figure 1). Disaggregated by country, the perception of GBV is most noticeable in Angola (62%) and Namibia (58%), while the population of Benin (22%) and Ghana (22%) think that GBV is less widespread in their country (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Manifestation of gender-based violence in Africa

Source: Authors based on data from Afrobarometer round 9, 2023

However, within countries, in some regions, the level of GBV is low compared to more violent regions (80%) (Table 1). This situation is driven by the promotion of sexist behavior.

Indeed, a third (30%) of respondents approve of a man disciplining a woman through acts of violence (Figure 1). This also reflects the scale of the phenomenon.

Figure 2: Perception of GBV by country

Source: Authors based on data from Afrobarometer round 9, 2023

According to the results of the descriptive statistics, the Poverty indicator shows that, on average, 38% of people in the regions are considered to be living in poverty.

The average age of our sample is 38, which represents the average age of individuals in all regions, with a minimum average age of 27 and a maximum average age of 63.

The table reveals an average unemployment rate of 31.9%, reaching 80.09% in some regions. On average, 41% of individuals in the regions have achieved at least secondary education, and over 79.40% in the most highly educated regions.

Statistics show that the average proportion of people

declaring a government presence is 40.9%, with a minimum of 3.10% in some regions.

On average, 44.5% of people reported a police presence in their locality, with a minimum of 0.4% in some regions.

These descriptive statistics give us an initial understanding of the characteristics of our sample and the variables under study. They provide an overview of general trends and variations in the variables. Note also that the correlation matrix obtained (in appendix) shows a low correlation between the variables. This helps reduce the problem of multi-collinearity, thereby enhancing the model's stability.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Fre violence	305	0.376	0.176	0	0.799
Poverty	305	0.38	0.182	0	1
Average Age	305	37.587	4.875	27	63
Unemployment	305	0.319	0.165	0	0.809
Education	305	0.411	0.141	0	0.794
Media	305	0.39	0.174	0	1
Social networks	305	0.4	0.218	0	0.915
Presence gov	215	0.409	0.279	0.031	1
Police presence	257	0.445	0.239	0.004	1
Urban	269	0.412	0.249	0.069	1
Harcel	305	0.527	0.162	0	0.914
Effort gov	305	0.67	0.109	0.401	0.816
Ps police	305	0.815	0.088	0.605	0.928
Democracy	305	0.466	0.119	0.15	0.695

Source: Authors based on Afrobarometer round 9 data

5. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Gender-based violence can be explained both by differences between states (inter-group variability) and between regions within the same country (intra-group variability). The results presented are based on a multi-level analysis of the determinants of GBV in Africa, using data from the ninth wave of the Afrobarometer. Three models were examined: the empty model, model 1 and model 2.

The empty model, the first model, also known as variance decomposition, without explanatory variables is used in this respect to assess the share of relative variance attributable to regions and states. The results of the inter-class variance (ICC) indicate that 49% of the differences in levels of gender-based violence can be explained by inter-country differences.

The remaining 51% can be explained by differences in levels of GBV between regions within the same country. These results show that GBV can be attributed to both levels to varying degrees. This confirms the interest and relevance of using the multi-level approach to analyze GBV in African countries.

Analysis of the multilevel regression results in Table 2 offers interesting economic implications for perceptions of gender-based violence in Africa.

The results of model 1 (regional level), show that regions with a high proportion of poor people are associated with an increase in the perception of gender-based violence. This suggests that socio-economic factors, such as economic insecurity and financial vulnerability, may play a key role in

the manifestation of gender-based violence. This lack of economic resources generally places women and girls in situations of great vulnerability to violence. These findings are similar to those of NdiAye (2021). According to the results, harassment of victims is a breeding ground for GBV. Indeed, fear of stigmatization often discourages victims from reporting their aggressors. Unfortunately, this situation does not discourage acts of gender-based violence.

Although the results did not show significant effects of unemployment and education on gender-based violence, it is important to note that these factors play a key role in women's economic empowerment. Better education and fair employment opportunities can help reduce gender inequalities and promote women's empowerment, which in turn can reduce levels of violence.

Media and social networks play a growing role in contemporary society (Ikiz, 2018). The low significance suggests that these factors are under-exploited in Africa to play their full role. Media and social networks can be used as powerful tools to raise awareness and educate individuals about non-violence and women's rights. Awareness-raising campaigns and media initiatives can help to change attitudes and behavior with regard to GBV. On the other hand, misuse of social networks can encourage GBV. In the absence of regulations on social networks, women and girls are increasingly exposed to GBV (Alava, Frau-Meigs, & Hassan, 2018)

At the national level (model 2), the State's commitment to reducing gender-based violence and making acts of violence

against women a criminal offence significantly contribute to the reduction of GBV.

The negative and significant coefficient of the "Effort_gov" variable indicates that government efforts for women's rights and equality are associated with a decrease in the perception of gender-based violence. This underlines the importance of specific government policies and measures to protect women from violence and promote their equality. Investments in educational programs, awareness-raising campaigns, victim support services and legislative reforms can help reduce gender-based violence.

The negative and significant coefficient of the variable "Ps_police" (Police taking gender-based violence seriously) indicates that the perception that women reporting gender-based violence are taken seriously by the police is associated with a decrease in gender-based violence. This underlines the importance of a sensitive and responsive law enforcement and justice system in combating gender-based violence. Training law enforcement officers in gender sensitivity, taking victims' needs into account and combating sexist stereotypes can foster better response and greater confidence among women in the justice system.

While poverty, social networks and harassment of victims encourage gender-based violence, traditional media, government efforts and consideration of GBV acts significantly deter it. This can be accompanied by the introduction of victim support services and violence prevention measures.

Table 2: Multi-level model results

Variables	(1) Empty model	(2) Model 1	(3) Model 2
Fixed effects			
Poverty		.241*** (.07)	.233*** (.068)
Average_Age		-.004* (.002)	-.003 (.002)
Unemployment		.074 (.08)	.051 (.077)
Education		-.051 (.089)	-.055 (.085)
Media		-.217** (.1)	-.202** (.094)
Reseau_sociaux		.186** (.075)	.2*** (.073)
Presence_gov		.043 (.048)	.045 (.047)
Presence_police		-.051 (.053)	-.046 (.052)
Urban		.023	.009

		(.04)	(.039)
Harcel		.209*** (.066)	.206*** (.064)
Effort_gov			-.71*** (.161)
Ps_police			-.607*** (.224)
Democracy			-.095 (.144)
_cons	.385*** (.027)	.363*** (.111)	1.344*** (.229)
Random effects			
lns1_1_1:_cons	-2.191*** (.182)	-2.133*** (.195)	-2.839*** (.277)
lnsig_e:_cons	-1.963*** (.042)	-2.116*** (.056)	-2.112*** (.056)
Comments	305	184	184

Standard errors are in parentheses

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Sources: authors based on Afrobarometer round 9 data

6. CONCLUSION

This study, based on a multi-level analysis of the determinants of gender-based violence in Africa, highlighted several significant factors. Poverty, governmental efforts, the seriousness with which police are taken, and the influence of the media and social networks were identified as important variables in the perception of gender-based violence. These findings have clear economic and political implications for combating this form of violence in Africa.

From an economic point of view, poverty reduction plays a crucial role in the prevention of gender-based violence. Policies aimed at improving the socio-economic conditions of populations, particularly women, can help reduce their vulnerability and strengthen their financial autonomy, thereby reducing power inequalities and situations conducive to violence. This requires investment in education, the creation of decent jobs, access to financial services and the enhancement of professional skills.

The results also underline the importance of government efforts in promoting women's rights and equality. Governments must adopt specific policies and programs to protect women from violence and ensure their equal participation in all aspects of social, economic and political life. This may include legislative reforms, awareness-raising campaigns, victim support services and violence prevention measures.

Taking the police seriously is an essential aspect of the fight against gender-based violence. Law enforcement officers need to be trained to be gender-sensitive, to listen and to take into account the specific needs of victims of gender-based violence. This will help to improve police response, increase

women's confidence in the justice system and promote the reporting of acts of violence.

Finally, the media and social networks can play an important role in raising awareness, social mobilization and disseminating information on gender-based violence. Online awareness campaigns, responsible journalism initiatives and the promotion of a positive discourse on equality and non-violence can help change social norms and reduce violent behavior.

In summary, this study highlights the economic and political implications of combating gender-based violence in Africa. The findings highlight the need to invest in poverty reduction, strengthen government efforts, improve police response and use the media and social networks responsibly. These implications are crucial to promoting and protecting women against violence and creating fairer, more inclusive societies in Africa.

REFERENCES

1. Abrahams, N., Jewkes, R., Laubscher, R., & Hoffman, M. (2006). Intimate partner violence: Prevalence and risk factors for men in Cape Town, South Africa. *Violence and victims*, 21(2), 247-264. doi:10.1891/vivi.21.2.247
2. Abramsky, T., Watts, C. H., & Garcia-Moreno, C. (2011). What factors are associated with recent intimate partner violence? Findings from the WHO multi-country study on women's health and domestic violence. *BMC public health*, 11(1), 1-17. doi:https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-11-109

3. Alava, S., Frau-Meigs, D., & Hassan, G. (2018). Comment qualifier les relations entre les médias sociaux et les processus de radicalisation menant à la violence?: Note de synthèse internationale. *Quaderni*, 39-52. doi:https://doi.org/10.4000/quaderni.1137
4. Amber, P., Palermo, T., & Bredenkamp, C. (2011). Peterman, A., PalermEstimates and determinants of sexual violence against women in the Democratic Republic of Congo. *American journal of public health*, 101(6), 1060-1067. doi:https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2010.300070
5. Antai, D., & Adaji, S. (2012). Community-level influences on women's experience of intimate partner violence and terminated pregnancy in Nigeria: a multilevel analysis. *C pregnancy and childbirth*, 12(1), 1-15. doi:https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2393-12-128
6. Arzenšek, A., Košmrlj, K., & Širca, N. (2014). Slovenian young researchers' motivation for knowledge transfer. *Higher education*, 68, 185-206. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-013-9702-0
7. Bleck, J., Palermo, T., & Peterman, A. (2014). Tip of the iceberg: reporting and gender-based violence in developing countries. *American journal of epidemiology*, 179(5), 602-612. doi:https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwt295
8. Bressoux, P. (2007). L'apport des modèles multiniveaux à la recherche en éducation. *Éducation et didactique*(1-2), 73-88. doi:https://doi.org/10.4000/educationdidactique.168
9. Caron, J., & Guay, S. (2005). Soutien social et santé mentale: concept, mesures, recherches récentes et implications pour les cliniciens. *Santé mentale au Québec*, 30(2), 15-41. doi:https://doi.org/10.7202/012137ar
10. Dequiré, A.-F. (2019). La violence faites aux femmes dans le monde: une pandémie? *Pensée plurielle*(2), 21-33. doi:https://doi.org/10.3917/pp.050.0021
11. Dwokin, S., Hatcher, A., & Colvin Chris et al. (2013). Impact of a gender-transformative HIV and antiviolence program on gender ideologies and masculinities in two rural, South African communities. *Men and masculinities*, 16(2), 181-202. doi:https://doi.org/10.1177/1097184X12469878
12. Fufu, E., Jewkers, R., & Roselli Tim et al. (2013). Prevalence of and factors associated with male perpetration of intimate partner violence: findings from the UN Multi-country Cross-sectional Study on Men and Violence in Asia and the Pacific. *I*(4), e187-e207. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(13)70074-3
13. Garcia-Moreno, C., Pallitto, C., Devries, K., Stöckl, H., Watts, C., & Abrahams, N. (2013). *Global and regional estimates of violence against women: prevalence and health effects of intimate partner violence and non-partner sexual violence*. World Health Organization.
14. Garcia-Moreno, C., Jansen, H., Ellsberg, M., Heise, L., & Watts, C. (2006). Prevalence of intimate partner violence: findings from the WHO multi-country study on women's health and domestic violence. *The lancet*, 368(9543), 1260-1269. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(06)69523-8
15. Hox, J. (1995). *Applied multilevel analysis. TT-publikaties*. TT-publikaties.
16. Igulot, P. (2022). Sexual and gender-based violence and vulnerability to HIV infection in Uganda: Evidence from multilevel modelling of population-level HIV/AIDS data. *Social Sciences*, 11(7), 307. doi:https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci11070301
17. Ikiz, S. (2018). Les violences à l'encontre des femmes sur les réseaux sociaux. *Topique*(2), 125-138. doi:https://doi.org/10.3917/top.143.0125
18. Jewkes, R. (2002). *The lancet*, 359(9315), 1423-1429. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(02)08357-5
19. Jewkes, R., & Morrell, R. (2010). Gender and sexuality: emerging perspectives from the heterosexual epidemic in South Africa and implications for HIV risk and prevention. *Journal of the International AIDS society*, 13, 1-11.
20. Jewkes, R., Sikweyiya, Y., Morrell, R., & Dunkle, K. (2011). The relationship between intimate partner violence, rape and HIV amongst South African men: a cross-sectional study. *PLoS one*, 6(9), e24256.
21. Jewkes, R., Sikweyiya, Y., & Morell, R. (2011). The relationship between intimate partner violence, rape and HIV amongst South African men: a cross-sectional study. *PLoS one*, 6(9), e24256. doi:https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0024256
22. Johnson, K., & Kishor, S. (2004). *Profiling domestic violence: a multi-country study*. Récupéré sur https://anrows.intersearch.com.au/anrowsjspui/handle/1/19748
23. Krug, E., Dahlberg, L., Mercy, J., & et al. (2002). *Rapport mondial de la violence et la santé*. Genève: WHO.
24. Martin, H. (2006). Émile Ellberger: La tragédie répétée. Hommage à toutes les femmes victimes de violences sexuelles en temps de guerre 1. *Nouvelles questions féministes*, 25(3), 147-149. doi:https://doi.org/10.3917/nqf.253.0147

25. Mekonnen, S., & Abeya, S. (2019). Sexual violence and associated factors among female students of preparatory schools in Modjo and Bishoftu towns of East Showa Zone, Oromia state, Ethiopia. *Rehabilitation, 4*(3), 44-53. doi: 10.11648/j.rs.20190403.12

26. Ndiaye, N. (2021). Violences basées sur le genre en Afrique de l’Ouest: cas du Sénégal, du Mali, du Burkina Faso et du Niger. *Séries FES sur la Paix et la Sécurité en Afrique, (42)*, 21-23. 42, 21-23. Récupéré sur <https://www.enda-sante.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/17675-20210510.pdf>

27. Novak, M., & Marko, P. (2017). Using a multilevel modelling approach to explain the influence of economic development on the subjective well-being of individuals. *Economic research-Ekonomska istraživanja, 30*(1), 705-720. doi:10.1080/1331677X.2017.1311229

28. Peterman, A., Palermo, T., & Bredenkamp, C. (2011). Estimates and determinants of sexual violence against women in the Democratic Republic of Congo. *American journal of public health, 101*(6), 1060-1067. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2010.300070>

29. Ryckmans, H., & Maquestiau, P. (2008). Population et développement: égalité de genre et droits des femmes. *Monde en développement*(2), 67-82. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3917/med.142.0067>

30. Sandis, E. E. (2006). United Nations measures to stop violence against women. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences, 1087*(1), 370-383. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences, 1087*(1), 370-383. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1385.004>

31. Schyns, P. (2002). Wealth of nations, individual income and life satisfaction in 42 countries: A multilevel approach. *Social Indicators Research, 60*(1), 5-40. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1021244511064>

32. Tiruye, T., Harris, M., Chojentya, C., & al. (2020). Determinants of intimate partner violence against women in Ethiopia: A multi-level analysis. *PLoS one, 15*(4), e0232217. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0232217>

33. Vyas, S., & Watts, C. (2009). How does economic empowerment affect women's risk of intimate partner violence in low and middle income countries? A systematic review of published evidence. *Journal of International Development. The Journal of the Development Studies Association, 21*(5), 577-602. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/jid.1500>

34. WHO. (2013). *WHO report on the global tobacco epidemic, 2013: enforcing bans on tobacco advertising, promotion and sponsorship*. World Health Organization.

35. Yount, K. M., & Carrera, J. S. (2006). Female genital cutting and reproductive experience in Minya, Egypt. *Medical Anthropology Quarterly, 20*(2), 182-211. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1525/maq.2006.20.2.182>

Appendix

Pairwise correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)
(1) VBG	1.000													
(2) poverty	0.270	1.000												
	*													
(3) Average_Age	-	-	1.000											
	0.138	0.104												
	*	*												
(4) Unemployment	0.258	0.334	-	1.000										
	*	*	0.093											
			*											
(5) Education	0.112	-	-	0.056	1.000									
	*	0.032	0.190	*										
			*											
(6) media	-	-	0.094	-	0.258	1.000								
	0.113	0.398	*	0.243	*									
	*	*		*										
(7) social_networks	-	-	0.001	-	0.336	0.703	1.000							
	0.027	0.337		0.141	*	*								
		*		*										
(8) Presence_gov	0.027	-	0.002	-	0.265	0.364	0.264	1.000						
		0.086		0.123	*	*	*							
		*		*										
(9)	0.054	-	-	-	0.167	0.144	0.174	0.516	1.000					

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Presence_police	*	0.219	0.012	0.022	*	*	*	*									
		*															
(10) Urban	0.055	-	-	0.058	0.040	0.034	0.086	-	-	1.000							
	*	0.051	0.035	*			*	0.018	0.091								
		*							*								
(11) harassment	0.119	-	-	0.054	-	-	0.090	0.048	0.104	-	1.000						
	*	0.013	0.012	*	0.039	0.001	*	*	*	0.031							
(12) effort_gov_n	-	0.075	0.089	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.234	1.000					
	0.408	*	*	0.028	0.161	0.084	0.042	0.047	0.005	0.203	*						
	*			*	*	*	*	*	*	*							
(13) ps_police_n	-	-	-	-	-	0.255	0.320	0.022	-	0.021	0.171	0.081	1.000				
	0.337	0.371	0.014	0.248	0.075	*	*		0.091	*	*	*					
	*	*		*	*				*								
(14) Democracy	-	-	0.053	0.024	-	0.091	-	0.059	0.058	-	-	0.142	0.098	1.000			
	0.153	0.203	*		0.199	*	0.154	*	*	0.216	0.007	*	*				
	*	*			*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*				

* shows significance at $p < .5$

Sources: authors based on Afrobarometer round 9 data